

Expert Interviews - Benchmarking Transcription Conventions

Because the analysis for this study is not a discourse analysis but a qualitative content analysis, there are fewer transcription rules needed. These transcription conventions have been adapted on the basis of the conventions in ten Have, P. (2007) *Doing conversation analysis, a practical guide*. London: Sage.

Convention	Description
-	Nothing is changed about what is said, even if the speaker makes incorrect sentence constructions, grammatical errors, or hesitations. - The transcription follows the conventions of standard written language (capital letters, periods, commas, question marks, and exclamation points).
(xxx) or (?)	A speaker says something that the transcriber/researcher cannot understand.
(nn)	An anonymised name.
(laughs)	Characterisation of a non-verbal activity or other noticeable occurrences (cough, clear throat, ironic; phone rings, door slams shut).
[hip throw]	An addition made afterward by the transcriber/researcher as an explanation, translation, etc.
-	Only in cases of extremely noticeable emphasis or elongation are the following additional conventions used.
(2.5)	The approximate duration of long pauses (in this case, a pause of 2 and a half seconds). No micropauses.
ACcent	The speaker clearly emphasizes the text written in capital letters (words, a word, part of a word, etc.).
re::ally	The relevant (consonant) sound is noticeably longer than usual for this speaker.

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